

Supplemental Data 3
(Context of the holotype and paratype of
***Climactichnites blackberriensis* Gass and Noffke, 2026)**
for
New ichnotaxa from the tidal flat facies of the Cambrian Elk Mound Group,
Wisconsin, USA

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Silicone molds showing from which parts of the two trails they were made. The larger two molds (MPM P39662 and P39664) are from two positions of the holotype. MPM P39666 and P39668 are from two positions of the paratype.

Portion of holotype with scyphozoans and sedimentary structures.

Scyphozoans and sedimentary structures near the type specimens.

Portions of both type specimens with scyphozoans and sedimentary structures.

Portion of holotype with scyphozoans (one questionable) and sedimentary structures.

Portion of holotype with scyphozoans and sedimentary structures.

Portion of holotype with scyphozoans and sedimentary structures.

Scyphozoan? and ripple marks.

Portion of holotype with scyphozoans and sedimentary structures.

Holotype and paratype with scyphozoans and sedimentary structures.